

International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Scientific Research (IJAESR)

ISSN: 2349 -3607 (Online) , ISSN: 2349 -4824 (Print)

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ASSESSMENT OF HEAVY METAL CONTAMINATION IN SOIL IN AND AROUND BIDADI INDUSTRIAL AREA, RAMANAGAR DISTRICT

R. Madhusudhan¹, M.Inayathulla²

¹ Associate Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Dr AIT, Bangalore, India

² Associate Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, UVCE, Bangalore, India

ABSTRACT

The industrial area in generally is witnessed by red sandy soil. The soil covers extends up to 1 to 2 m below the ground level. It is porous, non sticky and non clayey. This area is located on a highly undulating terrain. The highly undulating topography with dendritic nature has given rise to the origin of many hydrological varying characters. The pollution of soil is a source of danger to the health of people, even to those living in cities. The anthropogenic pollution caused by heavy industries enters plants then goes through the food chain and ultimately endangers human health. Due to industrialization, the pollution load for water, air and soil has increasing day by day. The present study was undertaken on soil contamination in Bidadi Industrial Area, Bidadi, Ramanagara Taluk and District. To find out the heavy metal pollution in soil we carried out the research work by collecting soil samples from different places in Industrial Area. In the present study it reveals that the heavy metal concentrations are at the nearby maximum level. The results shows that Zinc varies from 0.06 to 4.5 mg/kg, Copper varies from 0.29 to 6.84 mg/kg, Manganese varies from 0.94 to 32.14 mg/kg, Iron varies from 2.27 to 28.96 mg/kg, Boron varies from 0.12 to 0.5 mg/kg, Cadmium varies from 0.01 to 0.04 mg/kg, Chromium varies from 0.11 to 0.63 mg/kg, Alluminium found in the range of 21.5 to 77.8 mg/kg, P₂O₅ is found to be varies from 12 to 96.3 mg/kg, K₂O varies from 15.4 to 117 mg/kg, Organic Carbon is found to be varies from 0.09 to 0.81 and Electric Conductivity varies from 0.04 to 0.22. But from results the value of lead is NIL in most of the samples which is taken out from the Industrial Area. Soil pH varies from 6.30 to 7.50 and is acidic to near neutral and alkaline in nature. Soil pH significantly affects the solubility and mobility of these metals, as most of the metals are soluble in acid soils than in neutral or slightly basic soils. The methodology used has proved to be a useful tool to separate geological and anthropogenic causes of variation in soil heavy metal content and to identify common pollution sources.

Key words: Soil contamination, Heavy metals, Industries-Bidadi

INTRODUCTION

Soil is a very essential component for all the living organisms. Especially for plants it is considered as basic living factor. Soil serves as a nutrient media for the growth of plants. In soil we can observe so many elements. Sometimes these elements occur naturally for certain extent but in some time they will enter through the human interference with the soil by so many processes. Physicochemical properties of soils depend on both natural and anthropogenic factors, together acting over different spatial and temporal scales. Natural pedological process like rock weathering and organic matter decomposition are related to parent material, geomorphology of the area, presence of vegetation, the climatic conditions and other interactions with the environment. The effects

of these processes are strictly time-dependent and exposed in a quite complex structure of soils. In contrast, soil management practices significantly affect pedological properties by changing soil structure mechanically due to agricultural and urban activities, and by changing composition through pollution load. The presence of any element in a fatal concentration in the soil could be due to both natural and anthropogenic factors; therefore it is often quite difficult to discriminate among the different causes. The parent material largely influences heavy metal content in many soil types, with concentration sometimes exceeding the critical values. Heavy metals are natural constituents of the Earth's crust. In this type of input of unwanted things to the soil is the major problem with heavy metals. A number of these elements are biologically essential and are introduced into aquatic enrichments by various anthropogenic activities. Main anthropogenic sources of heavy metals exist in various industrial point sources. Heavy metals once introduced to the environmental systems, which may be lead to change over in whole chain systems in natural systems. Heavy metals may chemically or physically interact with the naturally occurring compounds, which changes their chemical forms of existence in the environment and lead to different effects.

It is well known that micronutrients such as Iron (Fe), Manganese (Mn), Copper (Cu), Zinc (Zn) and Boron (B) are essential metals for plant growth and yield. However, the plants may accumulate the heavy metals present in the soils but some of the elements like Cadmium (Cd), Nickel (Ni), Chromium (Cr) and Lead (Pb) are not essential for the plant growth, but may cause serious problems to the environment when they are in more in concentration. The concentration of heavy metals in soil solution plays a critical role in controlling the availability of ions to plants. Long-term and extensive use of agricultural land with frequent application of pesticides will result in heavy metal accumulation in the top soil. A soil pollution assessment becomes very complex when different sources of contamination are present and their products are variably distributed. In these cases the spatial variability of heavy metal concentrations in soils is basic information for identifying the possible sources of contamination and to delineate the strategies of site remediation. A detailed appraisal of the characteristics of urban soils points out that soils in urban and sub urban areas are frequently disturbed and subjected to mixing, filling and contamination with inorganic components and organic residue.

Heavy metals may be derived from many different sources to the urbanized area. One of the most important heavy metals sources is vehicle emission. Three main factors known to influence the levels in soil samples, which have been reported are traffic, industry and weathered materials. Topsoil and dusts in urban areas are indicators of heavy metal contamination from atmospheric deposition. It has been noted that location close to the roads are severally polluted by heavy metals. These heavy metals are toxic to human beings.

Table 1: Content of various elements in Soils

METALS	SELECTED AVERAGE FOR SOILS (mg/kg)	COMMON RANGE FOR SOILS (mg/kg)
Al	71,000	10,000-300,000
Fe	38,000	7,000-550,000
Mn	600	20-3,000
Cu	30	2-100
Cr	100	1-1000
Cd	0.06	0.01-0.70
Zn	50	10-300
As	5	1.0-50
Se	0.3	0.1-2
Ni	40	5-500
Ag	0.05	0.01-5
Pb	10	2-200
Hg	0.03	0.01-0.3

Source: (Lindsay, 1979; Murthy, 2008)

STUDY AREA

For the present study Bidadi Industrial Area was selected. Bidadi Industrial Area is 2km from SH-17. It is located at $N12^{\circ}47'$ and $E77^{\circ}23'$ and in the north-eastern part of the Ramanagara Taluk, Ramanagara District. A number of villages surrounding the Industrial Area are Anchipura, Abbanakuppe, Bannigere, Maregowdana Doddi, Byramangala, Shanamangala, Parasanapalya, Thimmegowdana Doddi and Vrishbhavathipura. Industrial area covers 852 acres. Ramanagara Taluk covers 62,930 hectares of geographical area and consists of 4 Hoblies namely Bidadi, Kasaba, Kailancha and Kootgal. The taluk had 126 villages, 23 Gram Panchayats and Municipal Council. According to the 2011 census, total population is approximately 3.5 lakhs. Detailed survey was conducted to identify the features of the terrain for collecting the soil samples for its assesment. The survey was conducted by visiting each industrial plot and surrounding the industries by identifying the existing situation in Bidadi industrial area.

Figure 1: Bird's Eye View of Bidadi Industrial Area

Fig.2 Key map of the study area

FIELD SURVEY

In field survey, the reconnaissance survey has been carried out for soil samples collection and latitude-longitude values of all industries present in and around Bidadi Industrial Area has been recorded by using the GPS (Global Positioning System) device and identified the points of sampling in the Industrial Area by enquiring the details present inside and outside the industry.

Materials and methods

SAMPLE COLLECTION

A systematic soil sampling program was conducted which includes a total of 21 samples. To avoid influence from various arbitrary surface conditions like waste and humus and to assure natural in place soil, the selected depth of sampling is from 10 to 15 cm below the surface to 25 cm depth. Normally, anthropogenic pollutants contaminate the upper layer of soil. In case of natural pollutant, the entire soil at all depths shows high level of metal enrichment. Bidadi Industrial Area is entirely divided into 21 blocks. The soils were taken from geographically distributed entire Industrial Area at the equal intervals of 21 blocks. The precise locations of the sampling points were determined in the field through the GPS (Global Positioning System) device. The exact longitude and latitude of the sampling sites has been determined by using this device. Sampling was carried out by using digging equipments. The soil samples were collected in polythene covers and brought to the laboratory. The soil samples were air dried and kept in oven for about 48 hours at 60⁰C. The dried samples were then disaggregated with mortar and pestle and were finely powdered to -250 mesh size using a swing grinding mill to make the sample homogeneous. In homogenized sample, the surface layer should represent the bulk specimen; it is an essential step to get accurate analytical data, pH of soil suspension using 1:1 soil to water ratio was determined by the method recommended in soil survey manual, 1993. Weighing of sample was accomplished using analytical balance with precision as low as 0.0001g. Aliquots of about 1gm of soil sample were digested with tri-acid mixture (Nitric Acid, Perchloric acid and Sulphuric Acid) for heavy metal analysis.

INSTRUMENTATION & ANALYSIS OF SOIL

The samples were analyzed for pH, Electric Conductivity (EC), Organic Content (OC), Phosphorous (P₂O₅), Potash (K₂O), Zinc (Zn), Copper (Cu), Manganese (Mn), Iron (Fe), Boron (B), Cadmium (Cd), Chromium (Cr), Lead (Pb) and Aluminium (Al). The samples were analyzed as per standard methods for examination of soil. The DTPA Extractant solution is used for the analysis of the samples. The above parameters are analyzed by following methods:

- | | |
|--|---|
| • pH | -Potentiometric Method |
| • Electric Conductivity (EC) | -Bridge Conductivity Method |
| • Organic Content (OC) | -Volcali and Black Wet Oxidization Method |
| • Phosphorous (P ₂ O ₅) | -Brass / Olscen Method |
| • Potash (K ₂ O) | -Ammonia Acetate Method |
| • Boron | -Hot Water Method |
| • Zinc (Zn) | -Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer Method |
| • Copper (Cu) | -Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer Method |
| • Manganese (Mn) | -Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer Method |
| • Iron (Fe) | -Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer Method |
| • Cadmium (Cd) | -Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer Method |
| • Chromium (Cr) | -Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer Method |
| • Lead (Pb) | -Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer Method |
| • Aluminium (Al). | -Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer Method |

SOIL SAMPLE ANALYSIS

Table 2: Analytic result of heavy metal concentration in Bidadi industrial area (mg/kg)

Sl. No	pH	Zn	Cu	Mn	Fe	B	Cd	Cr	Pb	Al	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	OC	EC
1	6.90	2.25	3.05	16.26	25.08	0.16	0.03	0.17	0	45.3	46.70	41.20	0.47	0.04
2	7.30	2.52	1.73	11.09	9.87	0.22	0.02	0.11	0	61.3	34.30	37.10	0.44	0.05
3	7.40	0.21	0.81	5.22	5.11	0.18	0.01	0.24	0.01	63.4	27.40	60	0.32	0.08
4	6.80	1.13	1.96	32.14	17.63	0.20	0.03	0.21	0	62.9	28.90	55.50	0.33	0.05
5	6.70	1.85	0.90	14.08	9.15	0.16	0.04	0.18	0	38.5	45.50	41	0.45	0.08
6	6.30	2.54	2.77	24.66	28.96	0.28	0.04	0.12	0	37.3	96.30	27.10	0.51	0.04
7	6.90	0.17	0.59	13.45	3.14	0.14	0.03	0.26	0	44.2	23.30	33.70	0.49	0.06
8	7.20	0.08	0.29	6.48	5.37	0.12	0.03	0.63	0	21.5	12	15.40	0.10	0.06
9	6.90	0.66	1.64	29.52	9.34	0.42	0.03	0.29	0	64.6	29.80	75.30	0.60	0.05
10	6.70	0.49	0.83	27.96	13.69	0.46	0.01	0.12	0	24.9	30.40	117	0.76	0.07
11	7.0	0.18	0.61	9.29	3.41	0.40	0.02	0.11	0	57.6	40.70	37.90	0.22	0.14
12	7.40	0.71	1.09	10.98	8.74	0.22	0.03	0.12	0	43.4	30.70	31.70	0.44	0.09
13	7.20	0.79	1.49	22.34	8.40	0.36	0.01	0.15	0	47.1	51.40	52.70	0.29	0.14
14	7.50	0.03	0.05	0.94	2.27	0.34	0	0	0	27.2	20.60	16.50	0.14	0.12
15	7.20	0.23	0.99	9.79	3.90	0.30	0.02	0.30	0	77.8	42.30	38	0.17	0.06
16	6.60	0.06	0.35	12.06	5.45	0.28	0	0.21	0	24.9	34.50	18.10	0.09	0.22
17	7.20	0.41	0.31	5.99	4.05	0.34	0.02	0.18	0	36.7	28.60	27.70	0.23	0.12
18	7.30	0.71	1.36	15.93	9.76	0.30	0.04	0.22	0	60.6	28.90	29.70	0.41	0.05
19	7.20	0.92	0.88	13.29	5.37	0.28	0.02	0.14	0	45.3	47.60	39.50	0.38	0.06
20	7.10	4.50	6.84	22.24	23.06	0.34	0.01	0.17	0	37.6	53.20	76.30	0.81	0.05
21	6.40	1.91	2.33	20.54	15.92	0.50	0	0.16	0	37.8	41.90	47.90	0.59	0.04

Table 3: Correlation coefficients between metals

	pH	Zn	Cu	Mn	Fe	B	Cd	Cr	Pb	Al	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	OC	EC
pH	1.00													
Zn	-0.28	1.00												
Cu	-0.21	0.90	1.00											
Mn	-0.59	0.39	0.48	1.00										
Fe	-0.55	0.78	0.77	0.64	1.00									
Boron	-0.23	0.02	0.12	0.33	0.04	1.00								
Cd	-0.08	0.10	0.01	0.19	0.23	-0.51	1.00							
Cr	0.04	-0.25	-0.14	-0.07	-0.18	-0.40	0.29	1.00						
Pb	0.27	-0.17	-0.10	-0.27	-0.16	-0.23	-0.19	0.09	1.00					
Al	0.27	-0.03	0.05	0.11	-0.09	-0.04	0.28	0.00	0.26	1.00				
P ₂ O ₅	-0.51	0.59	0.50	0.38	0.66	0.16	0.18	-0.36	-0.14	0.02	1.00			
K ₂ O	-0.19	0.23	0.36	0.64	0.30	0.45	-0.18	-0.14	0.16	0.11	0.03	1.00		
OC	-0.35	0.65	0.66	0.65	0.61	0.30	0.11	-0.26	-0.08	-0.03	0.32	0.72	1.00	
EC	0.08	-0.47	-0.43	-0.36	-0.50	0.14	-0.48	-0.19	0.00	-0.30	-0.16	-0.28	-0.58	1.00

Table 4: summary of heavy metals concentration in soil (mg/kg)

	pH	Zn	Cu	Mn	Fe	B	Cd	Cr	Pb	Al	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	OC	EC
Minimum	6.30	0.06	0.29	0.94	3.14	0.12	0	0	0	21.5	12	15.4	0.09	0.04
Maximum	7.50	4.5	6.84	32.14	28.96	0.5	0.04	0.63	0.01	77.8	96.30	117	0.81	0.22
Average	7	1.06	1.47	15.44	10.36	0.285	0.024	0.204	0.01	45.71	37.85	43.78	0.39	0.08
Median	7.1	0.71	0.99	13.45	8.74	0.28	0.025	0.175	0.01	44.2	34.3	38	0.41	0.06
Standard deviation	0.34	1.28	1.47	8.53	7.67	0.11	0.01	0.12	0.01	15.4	17.1	23.72	0.2	0.04
Standard Value	6-8	1.00	0.20	2.00	4.50	0.50	0.70	64.0	70.0	50.0	22	120	0.75	1.0

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The individual data acquired for each element are shown in TABLE 6.1.1. The statistical analysis results are summarized as minimum, average, median and standard deviation of PH, Zn, Cu, Mn, Fe, B, Cd, Cr, Pb, Al, P₂O₅, K₂O ,OC, EC concentration (in mg/kg) and are graphically represented as below:

Graphical representation of soil quality parameters at different sampling locations

CONCLUSION

The samples were collected in **pre-monsoon** period from in and around Bidadi Industrial Area. 21 soil samples were collected. Analysis of soil samples from 21 sampling points in the Bidadi Industrial Area showed significant variations of heavy metals (Zn, Cu, Mn, Fe, B, Cd, Cr, Pb and Al).

Soil pH varies from 6.30 to 7.50 and is acidic to near neutral and alkaline in nature. Soil pH significantly affects the solubility and mobility of these metals, as most of the metals are soluble in acid soils than in neutral or slightly basic soils. The soils have the potential to retain further additional heavy metal loads in such pH conditions.

The results show that Zinc varies from 0.06 to 4.5 mg/kg, Copper varies from 0.29 to 6.84 mg/kg, Manganese varies from 0.94 to 32.14 mg/kg, Iron varies from 2.27 to 28.96 mg/kg, Boron varies from 0.12 to 0.5 mg/kg, Cadmium varies from 0.01 to 0.04 mg/kg, Chromium varies from 0.11 to 0.63 mg/kg, Aluminum found in the range of 21.5 to 77.8 mg/kg, P_2O_5 is found to be varies from 12 to 96.3 mg/kg, K_2O varies from 15.4 to 117 mg/kg, Organic Carbon is found to be varies from 0.09 to 0.81 and Electric Conductivity varies from 0.04 to 0.22. But from results the value of lead is NIL in most of the samples which is taken out from the Industrial Area. As evident from the above results, the values of Zn, Cu, Mn, Fe and Al are above the permissible limits. Hence we can say that the soil is considerably contaminated by heavy metals with their concentrations beyond standard values. These heavy metals have a tendency to bio magnify and induce long term adverse impact on eco-system in terms of bio-chemical and toxicological effect on human beings and other compositions of the planet. This study recommends periodic monitoring of soil environment for toxic metals in the study area.

REFERENCES

- A. K. Krishna, P. K. Govil, (2007). Soil contamination due to heavy metals from an industrial area of Surat, Gujarat, Western India. *Environmental Monitoring and assessment*, Vol 124 (1-3), pp263-275.
- Babu B. V. and Ramakrishna V. (2003). "Hazardous Waste Management In India" Birla Institute of Technology and Science Pilani – 333 031 (Rajasthan) India 26,.
- D Purushotham, Mahjoor Ahmad Lone, Mehnaz Rashid, A Narsing Rao and Shakeel Ahmed (2012). Deciphering heavy metal contamination zones in soil of a granitic terrain of southern India using factor analysis and GIS. *Journal of Earth System Science*, vol 121, (4), pp, 1059-1070.
- Divya Agarwal and Anil Kumar Gupta, (2011). Hazardous Waste Management : Analysis of Indian Scenario and Perspective Governance, *VSRD-TNTJ*, Vol. 2 (9), 2011, 484-495.
- M. Cos, kun, E. Steinnes, M.V. Frontasyeva, T.E. Sjobakk, S. Demkina, Heavy metal pollution of surface soil in the Thrace Region, Turkey, *Environ. Monit. Assess.* 119 (2006) 545–556.
- Raymond A. Wuana and Felix E. Okieimen (2011). Heavy metal in contaminated soils: A review of sources, chemistry, risks and best available strategies for remediation. *International Scholarly Research Notices, ISRN Ecology*, volume 2011 (2011), article 1D402647
- S. Srinivasa Gowd, M.Ramakrishna Reddy, P.K. Govil (2010), Assessment of heavy metal contamination in soils at Jajmau (Kanpur) and Unnao industrial areas of the Ganga Plain, Uttar Pradesh, India. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, vol 174, (1-3), pp, 113-121
- Shantanu K Dutta, V P Upadhyay, U. Sridharan. (2005). Environmental management of Industrial Hazardous Wastes in India. *Journal of Environ, Science and Engineering*, Vol 48, (2), pp, 143-150
- Shiva Kumar. D, Srikantaswamy S Heavy (2012). metals pollution assessment in industrial area soil of Mysore City, Karnataka, India, *International journal of applied science and engineering research*, vol-1 (4), pp, 604-611
- Vandana Parth, N. N. Murthya and Praveen Raj Saxenab (2011) - "Assessment of heavy metal contamination in soil around hazardous waste disposal sites in Hyderabad city (India): natural and anthropogenic implications"- *Journal of Environmental Research and Management* Vol. 2(2). pp. 027-034, August, 2011.